

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT OF THE TOURISM SECTOR IN UKRAINE

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ABSTRACT

The article considers strategic aspects of tourism sector management in Ukraine. Tourist industry of Ukraine is an important component of the economic and social development of the state. However, taking into account the existing risks, rapid changes and instability of the situation in the world and in the country, there is a need for a detailed analysis of the methods and methods of managing tourism activities at the state, regional level and at the level of tourist enterprises. It is determined that the greatest influence on the development of tourism in Ukraine have natural, human, financial resources, which are provided by social, economic, legal and organizational leverage. It is specified that modern strategic aspects of management are always effective and have a systemic character at the state and regional levels. Improving the management system at all levels will allow to effectively use tourism potential and develop the tourism industry.

Keywords: tourism, tourism industry, tourism enterprise management, tourism activity management, state regulation of tourism, tourism management, management system.

Formulation of the problem. Effective management in the tourism industry of Ukraine in conditions the crisis caused by the COVID-19 pandemic and Russian-Ukrainian war, requires search New Unconventional Approaches and Improvements available management methods. Ukraine has a significant potential for the development of international and domestic tourism, which is able to increase the positive image and attractiveness of the country in the international market of tourism services. Tourist the industry is a catalyst for social and economic development in the long term, providing a profitable part of the country's budget, improving the balance of payments, growth employment by creating additional jobs.

Tourism development has a positive impact on other activities with which closely cooperating and effective management appears mandatory component of entities that provide transportation, accommodation and food services, consumer services. Most an effective tool for the development of tourism industry is to create a management system that would was based on modern methods and approaches and corresponded to the current situation and realities of the present. The main purpose of the study is theoretical and scientific substantiation of modern technologies and tourism management techniques in Ukraine at the state and regional level and determining their role in improving the competitiveness of the tourism industry.

Analysis of recent research and publications. A significant contribution to the study of tourism management was made by foreign and domestic scientists, in particular V. Khoroshun, A. Dubova, O. Babchinskaya, A. Baldynyuk, L. Dyachenko, V. Kiptenko, O. King, M. Krachylo, G. Tkachuk, O. Kraynik, L. Dolzhikova-Polishchuk, I. Kirilluk. However, given the changes in XXI century., associated with risks, threats, challenges and global changes, the issue of management in the

tourism industry remains relevant and requires further research.

The purpose of the work. The purpose of writing the article is to substantiate the main strategic directions of development of the tourism sector in Ukraine.

Results. The tourism industry has acquired today a global phenomenon and is economic development potential of many countries the world, a channel of international cooperation and a component the life of most of the population. Events in Ukraine, since 2014, associated with the annexation of the Crimean peninsula and part of Lugansk and Donetsk region, in 2020 – with a severe crisis, caused by COVID-19 and in 2022 – the beginning full-scale invasion of the Russian Federation on the territory of Ukraine, require new approaches to the management of the tourism industry at the state and regional levels and at the level of activity tourist enterprises.

The theoretical and practical meaning of «management» – it is the influence of the control subject on the control object.

The subject of tourism management is the state authorities, and the object is tourist enterprises (travel agents and tour operators), and other enterprises and organizations taking participation in the formation of a tourist product, servicing and meeting the needs of tourists.

Practice shows that the development of tourism directly proportionally depends on effective management in this area at different levels and support by the state. The tourism industry is a set of different subjects of tourism activity (accommodation facilities, tourist complexes, food enterprises, transport organizations, institutions culture, sports, etc.) that provide reception, service and transportation of tourists [8, p. 22].

The tourism industry for the economy of Ukraine has of great importance, since it is one of the components of filling the state budget, creating additional

jobs, image enhancement countries at the international level, ensuring socio-economic development.

In general, we can determine that management – is a type of management that deals with conscious influence on labor resources carried out to achieve certain goals in the activities of the enterprise.

Methodological basis of management is:

- regularities and scientific laws (primarily in the fields of management, psychology, sociology, economics, public communications);
- regulatory framework (international and national legislation and standards);
- methodological management tools (functions, principles, techniques, methods, models, styles, mechanisms, technologies, machinery, programs, etc.);
- managerial decisions of specialists-managers (taken on the basis of their consciousness, knowledge, experience, desires, etc. within the business environment and national management system) [10, p. 427].

Combining the interests of tourism development at all hierarchical levels, the management system reflects a set of tourism management methods activity.

B. Baida believes that the management system tourism should include a certain kind of subsystems [1, p. 23]:

1) a subsystem of goals that combines the goals of the functioning and development of the tourism management system, its structural elements and tasks that are solved in the course of achieving the formulated goals;

2) objects of the tourism management system, including travel products, services, resources, markets, etc.;

3) subjects of the tourism management system – state tourism management bodies, local executive authorities, local authorities, regional state bodies, non-governmental organizations (public organizations), tourism enterprises;

4) subsystem of control provision in the sphere tourism, activities and actions necessary in the process of formation, implementation and development of the tourism management system.

Tourism activities include a significant number of financial, natural, human and other species resources and is provided by special legal, social, economic, organizational leverage. It is state regulation that has been associated with the necessary requirements, which will reflect the interests of society in modern socio-economic development [3, p. 23].

The Law of Ukraine "On Tourism" states that state regulation of tourism is the implementation of the State Set of Regulatory Measures and control over tourism activities with to ensure the protection of rights and legal interests of citizens, environmental protection, improving the level of tourist services and ensuring safety tourism. The Law enshrines the most important legislative provisions on the place and role of tourism in state, principles of implementation of state policy in the field of tourism [4].

Regulation of tourism in Ukraine is carried out at the level of diversified (multidisciplinary) the Ministry of Culture and Information Policy of Ukraine (MKIP), which directs and coordinates the activities of the State Development Agency Tourism in Ukraine (DART).

The mechanism of state regulation of the tourism industry should be considered as a set of organizational,

economic, legal and other methods, with which interrelated functions to ensure the sustainable development of tourism.

According to the scope of the methods of regulation of tourism activities are divided into methods: legal sphere, economic sphere, social sphere, scientific and educational sphere, sphere of tourism organization.

In order to popularize tourism, effective management and development of the tourism industry On March 16, 2017, the Government approved the Strategy for the Development of Tourism and Resorts for the period up to 2026, in which the conditions for the sustainable development of tourism and resorts are formed, which is fully consistent with the obligations of Ukraine within the framework of implementation Association Agreements between Ukraine and the EU.

The need to introduce a management system in the regions is due to decentralization processes. Unfortunately, the existing methods of management and regulation of tourism activities are not always effective and do not meet modern requirements and trends. Improvement is advisable to improve management efficiency mechanisms for managing tourist processes at the regional level, taking into account the priority areas of socio-economic development each region of Ukraine [7, p. 190].

For efficient maximum use tourism potential in regions and communities it is recommended to implement the Smart concept Tourist Destination, which is provided by the provisions the State Strategy for Regional Development 2021-2027 [9].

Smart Tourist Destination is an initiative of the European Commission aimed at supporting cities The EU in facilitating access to tourism and hospitality tourism products and services through technological innovation. Management includes ways that structure rules, norms and actions including regulation, support and control. Therefore, management can take many forms, guided by different motivations and have different results. Management allows you to develop purposefully, form appropriate structures, and processes and maintain interaction between stakeholders [11].

Using this approach provides an opportunity to achieve significant economic benefits without causing environmental and economic problems potentially tourist regions of Ukraine. Effective management of the tourism business at the regional level will contribute to the socio-economic development of communities.

A set of interrelated subjects of tourism activities, destinations, governing bodies, educational and scientific institutions and other organizations that have attitude to the development of tourism in the regional levels, infrastructure, and consumers tourist services makes it possible to form a regional tourist system [2, p. 116].

The organizational structure of the management of the tourism sector at the regional level is ensured by the effective activities of the relevant structural units. In regional state administrations operate departments or departments of culture and tourism. In some cases the staff of workers is significantly limited or does not correspond to the tourist potential of the region.

The conditions of administrative reform and the peculiarities of the industry require the transfer of the main part powers in state regulation policy tourism to local authorities, but the local authorities themselves do

not yet have the necessary labor and financial resources, including experience to take responsibility for the development of the industry in a certain territory. This is especially true of small towns and villages that in most cases have significant recreational and tourism resources for development tourism, but in the structure of their urban and rural councils no specialized units and qualified specialists that could perform obligations assigned to them [6].

In the organization of tourist travel is important place is occupied by tourist enterprises that do not can operate without a control system.

Effective management system ensures competitiveness and efficiency enterprise. Prerequisite for creation and promotion quality tourist product is the use of innovative technologies as a means of information exchange. Management of the tourism enterprise should be aimed at implementation optimal tourist product or service for achieving competitive advantages and ensuring vital activity. Components of the innovation activity of the enterprise should be directed to organization of creation of new tourist products, introduction of innovative technologies in production of services, introduction of new methods maintenance, bringing planned projects to the level of innovative.

Analyzing the achievements of NTP, we can distinguish the main innovative technological trends: Biometrics (biometrics), Blockchain (block chain), Robotics (robotics), AI (artificial intelligence), VR&AR (virtual and augmented reality), Chatbots (chat bots), Voice (voice), Self-driving (self-driving), Mobile (mobile). These innovations have long been in use and have their advantages.

The use of multifunctional mobile devices, bots, chatbots are examples of the specific application of innovative digital technologies in the field of tourism. They quickly become communication channels and can accompany tourist throughout his journey. Chatbots allow you to simultaneously serve a large number of requests, collect and store information about users. Development and support of chatbot costs much less than state maintenance employees, which increases access to service and save time.

Conclusions. Conclusions from this study and perspectives. Dynamic and unstable development of the tourism industry requires improvement of the mechanism management by finding new methods and improving existing approaches in management activities. When improving a modern system management must first take into account changes in the external environment, current trends development of related industries that have the greatest impact on the tourism sector, to introduce the latest information technology in the processes creation, implementation and consumption of a tourism product, which in the future will ensure the competitiveness of the industry at the national and international tourism market.

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